

NFDI4Objects

Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

Temporary Working Group (TWG)

Prototypical modelling of a provenance gazetteer for FAIR provision in a Wikibase

Chairs: Angela Berthold (MK, SPK); Florian Thiery (LEIZA)

Members (07.08.2024): Anja Gerber (KSW); Katharina Gucia-Klassen (Braunschweigisches Landesmuseum); Christoph Klose (MK, SPK); Juliane Kraske (DZK); Katharina Martin (MK, SPK); Jan Peuckert (MK, SPK); Sarah Wagner (FAU Erlangen)

SC-Decision: 28.06.2023

Designation of members by the Speaker: 07.08.2024

Bodies Involved: TA2, TA6, CC Provenance Research, CC Semantic Modelling & LOD, Deutsches Zentrum Kulturgutverluste, Braunschweigisches Landesmuseum

External Linking: Wikimedia Deutschland (via wikibase.cloud)

Aims and Objectives

The provenance data of objects in museum and collection databases include information on previous owners and sellers. These are people on the one hand and corporate bodies on the other. Some of these are stored in the object databases as authority data (VIAF, GND, Getty AAT etc.). Examples of this are Dr. Philipp Lederer¹ or Felix Schlessinger². However, some of them can only be found in the respective object databases and there is no open provision of these identifiers as URIs (since they are not included in the GND, for example). Examples of this (only linked in the NDP) are Zakaris Bezdikian³ or the corporate body Ignaz Storek (Brno)⁴. In the associated authority data thesauri, the entries for people and corporate bodies are linked, but again not to the objects associated with them. However, such a linking of personal and corporate data with the objects is an important tool in provenance research, as it allows the former collections of a previous owner to be reconstructed across today's institutional

¹ <https://n4o-prov.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q25>

² <https://n4o-prov.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q26>

³ <https://n4o-prov.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q20>

⁴ <https://n4o-prov.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q23>

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boundaries and various collecting interests⁵ (). The aim of this TWG is to test persons, corporate bodies and the link to the objects in a prototype manner in a Wikibase instance. In addition, persons and corporate bodies that do not have an external identifier are to be made available openly⁶. The results are to be queried from the Wikibase instance via an automated script and converted into a SKOS representation for the integration of the provenance gazetteer in DANTE. This exemplary workflow is to be described in white papers in such a generic way that it can be transferred to other object groups and projects. For this purpose, various participants will provide data on previous owners and sellers, particularly from the period 1933 to 1945. These are particularly suitable because a broad database is available in many collections at this time. In the community cluster Provenance Research, the wish was expressed to also include data from the area of colonial contexts, so that this should initially become a second thematic focus in the Wikibase. There is also likely to be some overlap between these two areas.

Out of Scope

This TWG does not generate any new authority data or concepts on persons and entities or other data relevant to provenance research. It simply evaluates a generic methodology within a Wikibase so that it can be transferred to other object groups and projects.

⁵ Example for a query: <https://tinyurl.com/2y764e53> and on a map: <https://tinyurl.com/2bd8q8a6>

⁶ Some examples already here in the test instance: <https://n4o-prov.wikibase.cloud>

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Intended Work Results

- Provenance Wikibase instance
- Whitepaper on Wikibase Modeling
- Script for transforming Wikibase entries in SKOS to integrate the provenance gazetteer in DANTE

Envisaged Commons Contributions

- Whitepaper
- Transformation Scripts